

The “At-Risk” Minority Students’ Perception And Attitude Towards Mathematics In Wenchi Municipality Of Ghana

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Abstract

The study assessed five "at-risk" students' mathematical attitudes. A 22-item questionnaire was administered to investigate how educational, psychological, and parental characteristics influenced "at-risk" children's poor performance. School data and questionnaires were organised into text, tables, and figures. Results revealed that students were not supervised at home to revise their math notes, complete homework, and do extra arithmetic tasks. Math teachers have not yet identified that pupils skip classes or do not study. Teachers must work together with parents to meet most educational needs and care about students, especially teens, to ensure high academic standards and student success.

Introduction

Scholars who have conducted studies on perception and attitude of students towards mathematics in different sites almost reported in general, of all students without taking cognisance of the “at-risk” minority group in the research (Armah, 2018; Armah & Asiedu-Addo, 2014; Berger et al., 2022; Kennedy et al., 2014; Mazana et al., 2019; and Mullis et al., 2016). This study rather seeks to explore only the minority group of “at-risk” students’ attitude and perception towards mathematics. There is little attention given to the “at-risk” minority group in the classroom during lesson delivery, and most teachers sometimes refer to such students as the ‘weak’ ones in class. What makes them not to grasp the content being taught has not been fully investigated, yet we classify them as ‘weak’ students. Again, what distract their attention in class, and at home to read and concentrate on their books are still yet to be uncovered. It is against these tenets that the researcher seeks to undertake a study on these “at-risk” students in mathematics lessons in the classroom. The researcher seeks to undertake a study on five “at-risk” students in a school, where all these students scored lowest in a just ended terminal examinations in mathematics.

1.1 Statement of the problem

At the end of each academic year, semester or term in a school calendar, comes end of term examinations administered to students to test their level of understanding based on all that were taught within the said period. In the conduct of the examinations, scores are allotted to the individual’s performances displayed during subject examinations, such as mathematics. It has always been the trend of teachers to rank who scored highest in a subject paper and who scored lowest in that particular paper. Those who score least in a paper are placed last in terminal reports of each class. Those who score least and are placed at last positions in the terminal reports are considered the “at-risk” students. The “at-risk” students normally score below average or display poor performance during examinations. The problem of what makes students to perform so low in mathematics during end of term examinations after prolonged weeks of teaching and learning in and outside the classroom, requires inquiry of study with the “at-risk” students serving as participants.

1.2 Objectives of the study

The main purpose of this study was to explore pedagogical, psychological, and parental factors that may have contributed to low performance of “at-risk” minority group of five students in mathematics. This research was not meant to be an intervention-oriented study, though the recommendations from this study could be taken to improve students’ performance in mathematics. Specifically intends to find out whether or not such students: (1) understand mathematics lessons taught in the classroom; (2) read their mathematics notes at home under the supervision of their parents; (3) pay rapt attention in class during mathematics lessons; (4) revise adequately for end of term examination, especially for mathematics.

2.0 Conceptual framework

Teaching pedagogy is the skills and methods adopted by a teacher in delivering a content to students and pupils in the classroom. Various pedagogical methods are applied during teaching. Notable among the pedagogical method are lecture method, teacher-centred method, learner-centred method, etc. The type of pedagogy adopted by a teacher is influenced by his/her belief and how the strategy will positively contribute to students' learning outcomes. Again, the pedagogy will depend on the level of students or learning at the receiving end of education. Basic school level normally uses to adopt teacher-centred approach because the teaching seems to impart knowledge. The teacher is also to be repository of knowledge and is able to transfer to students. Teachers at the basic school are again perceived by their students knowledgeable in their subject areas, and for that matter will always wait till the teachers teaches them a subject content before they learn.

If the teacher-centred approach is shifted a bit to incorporate student-centred approach to teaching the basic school, the results we see now will be improved. In the student-centred approach in teaching, the students rather play very active role in the teaching whereas, the teacher serves a guide or facilitator. Group presentations, group assignments, students' portfolios, and student field trips will facilitate academic enhancement of the students, especially in mathematics.

2.1 Parents contribution to students' education

Pundits have supported the idea of parental involvement as a major factor to improve academic achievement including social outcomes for children (Desforges & Abouchaar, 2003; Epstein, 2001; Hornby, 2011; Jeynes, 2007). One of the benefits researchers' highlight is that schools that do well are most often the ones that support and promote the involvement of parents and family members in children's schooling and education (Grant & Ray, 2010; Henderson & Mapp, 2002).

Jeynes (2007) defines parental involvement as "parental participation in the education process and experiences of their children." There is school-based parental involvement as well as home-based parental involvement. In this case, anyone assuming the position of parenting a child, and not necessarily biological parent, is a parent. Parent could also be a family member taking care of a child in schooling, who acts a guardian. The school-based parental involvement may include attending Parents-Teachers-Association (PTA) meetings, Parent-Teacher Interaction (PTI) meetings, and Parent Education Workshops in schools. The home-based parental involvement may include supervising children's homework, teaching children at home as much as possible, and listening to children as they read at home. Assigning homework to learners are as beneficial for several reasons. Assignments place more emphasis on the responsibility on learners to resolve their challenges at considerable pace in bringing self-satisfaction (Jongsma et al., 2003). The basic importance of parental involvement in children's education is to improve children's educational outcomes (Cox, 2005; Fan & Chen, 2001; Pomerantz et al., 2007). In children's education and schooling, the roles of parents' involvements cannot be understated. Parents create an environment outside the school to continue and reinforce the taught curriculum in school to facilitate learning (Robinson & Harris, 2014). This will go a long way to reducing student delinquency, and help improve discipline. It is said that parents who play active role in their children's education, promote academic growth, social enlightenment, and emotional growth.

The Wenchi municipality which has majority of the populace in the class of urban-poor, parents seemingly do not consider fulfilling their part of this task to ensuring upward improving in children's education. The reason could be attributed to economic hardships and uneven access to water and sanitation, housing and health, as well as education. This is evident during PTA meetings organised in the schools where parents' participation has always been on the low and the lack of cooperation that generates during discussions in such meetings. On the other some teachers are also contributing factors to parents' non-participations in school affairs of their wards. Bol and Berry III (2005) in their study revealed findings that some teachers have negative attitudes towards parents' involvement in curriculum and school instructions. One of their findings was that many teachers consider poor families as not having value for education or do not see education as a priority.

2.2 Classroom control and management

Classroom control and management in among the core responsibilities of a good teacher to ensure smooth teaching and learning. Teaching-and-learning is a two-way affair where a more knowledgeable individual guides a less knowledgeable person to cultivate his/her own understanding of a subject matter. When adolescent students do not pay attention in class during lesson, it could be attributed to Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) as described by Jongsma et al. (2003). For such students, assisting them to channel their energies in a positive direction will be beneficial for their academic advancement. Again, teachers should not overlook such students rather, they ought to be asked questions and be fully involved in the

lesson, especially in mathematics. This in a way will enhance their concentration to subject being taught in class. Another important aspect of classroom control and management will require the teacher to change sitting positions of students at any point during lessons. At another time the teacher can group students in seating for lessons, and with dynamism of the teacher, class control will facilitate teaching and learning to yield positive results.

2.3 Preparation towards mathematics examinations

The period allocated on the school's academic calendar for revision towards end of term or semester examinations are sometimes abused by students. It is around this time of the term or semester that students are expected to be in tranquil manner and reflect on all things taught within the term and recall all to better position themselves for examinations. Students rather think those periods are free periods; they talk to friends, do minimal reading and sometimes play on the school field. The ideal situation is for teachers in the various subjects to revise with the students and not allow students to revise on their own. Teachers could assign topics treated within the term to groups in the class for class presentation. In this case students will do peer-teaching to display their understanding on the subject matter under the guidance of the teacher as supervisor in the class presentations. Doing this will better psych the minds of the students to recall contents and do wonderfully well during examinations. Teachers are to take time to adequately prepare candidates before examinations (WAEC-Ghana, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020)

2.4 Mathematics in Ghanaian curriculum

As a subject in both junior high school (JHS) and senior high schools (SHS), mathematics is found to be useful and complements other subjects such as science, technical, vocational, economics, accounting, etc. The subject serves as one of the requirements on which admissions are offered to students to pursue second cycle education or tertiary level education. Mathematics is among the four core subjects studied at the basic school level in Ghana (Asiedu, 2009, 2018). If a JHS candidate fails to pass mathematics to obtain the required grade in the Basic Education Certificate Examinations (BECE), such candidate would not have a first-time admission to study at the SHS level. A re-sit (re-write) of the mathematics paper is allowed until the results become better. The same is applicable to SHS candidate requiring admission to study at the tertiary level.

Mathematics syllabus adopted for use in the Ghanaian junior high schools' premise on the rationale that "the mathematics syllabus is focused on attaining one crucial goal: to enable all Ghanaian young persons to acquire the mathematical skills, insights, attitudes and values that they will need to be successful in their chosen careers and daily lives. The new syllabus is based on the premises that all students can learn mathematics and that all need to learn mathematics. The syllabus is therefore, designed to meet expected standards of mathematics in many parts of the world".

Again, mathematics at the Senior High school (SHS) in Ghana builds on the knowledge and competencies developed at the Junior High School level. The student is expected at the SHS level to develop the required mathematical competence to be able to use his/her knowledge in solving real life problems and secondly, be well equipped to enter into further study and associated vocations in mathematics, science, commerce, industry and a variety of other professions" (Ministry of Education, 2010, 2020).

The two profile dimensions of mathematics as adopted by the syllabus JHS mathematics for teaching, learning and testing JHS students in Ghana are: Knowledge and understanding (KU), and application of knowledge (AK). According to the teaching syllabus, 30% attention is attributed to KU and 70% to AK. Knowledge is basically the ability to remember what is being taught and which constitutes the lowest level of learning process. Understanding is one's ability to grasp a content or subject matter in a pictorial, verbal, written or symbolic form.

3.0 Methodology

The design that suited this research was mixed methods approach. Specifically, the study dwells on an explanatory sequential mixed method to collect and analyze data. Initial data was collected quantitatively with help of the documents in the school such as school register, reports and continuous assessment to ascertain the total number of pupils in the school. After the stratification sampling to arrive at the sample population for the study, a qualitative approach was then adopted to continue with the research. The use of closed-end questionnaire was then used to collect data from the participants. The data was organized and presented in the form of text, tables, and figures. Last, the data presented was descriptively analyzed in a manner such that drawing conclusions and recommendations became a reference point for further research.

The school has an entire pupils' population of 112. Again, there are 12 teachers, 1 headmaster and 1 school proprietor. The non-teaching staff number up to 4 including kitchen staff and security personnel. The targeted target population included all the school pupils as the time of this research, totaling 112. Researchers (see, Amoani, 2005; Amoah and Eshun, 2015; McMillan and Schumacher, 1997; Osuala, 2001; Quartey et al., 2002) consider population as the universe group whom the findings of a research can be referred to in the general sense.

Sampling techniques used to obtain the sample for the study were stratification and purposive sampling with the following two characteristics: (1) pupils within each class groups who have experienced scoring lowest in just ended mathematics examination; and (2) pupils who could read and understand simple English text, with minimal coaching. The first criterion in the stratification gave a number of 9 pupils. But, for the purpose of the research where questionnaire will be used to collect data from the respondents, the second criterion scaled down the 9 pupils to only 5 pupils.

4.0 Findings

From the supported materials and results of the study it can be said that, the following factors accounted for the current conditions of the "at-risk" students in mathematics in school, at home after school: (1) Students do not understand when their mathematics teachers deliver maths lessons in the classroom. This could be one of the reasons why the "at-risk" students perform abysmally during mathematics examinations. A more serious issue arrives when the time is approaching exams period; at this point, the respondents could not understand their own handwritten notes on mathematics during revision; (2) Surprisingly, the respondents forget almost all the contents after they have been taught in class by their mathematics teachers. And, this is a really serious issue of concern that needs to be addressed to facilitate student learning. If the forgetfulness of subject matter at this adolescent stage of the students are not remedied, it will negatively affect them in their academics pursuant. Though not specified, it could be attributed to their excessive indulging and spending more time on social media at the expense of their books; (3) Students find it difficult in paying rapt attention in class during mathematics lessons. The results indicate that, they either talk to friends or have low interest in the mathematics as compared to other subjects. Due to their low likeness and interest in mathematics, they tend not ask questions in class; and (4) Students do not revise adequately for end of term examination, especially for mathematics. Per their answers, they do not work more examples when revising for mathematics examinations. This could also account for their low performance during mathematics examinations.

Figure 1: Students' conception of mathematics content during lessons

Source: Field data (2022)

In Figure 1, it is more evident that the students do not have much problem during mathematics classes in terms of class participation, teacher working more examples on the chalkboard or giving students more class work or assignments but, the problem arises after the lesson. It means that right after the mathematics lesson till the next day/time when they have the same lesson. About half of the students could not recollect whatever mathematics lesson they learnt the previous day/time. They seem to forget all. In this case it is serious to overlook this

situation why students forget all they learn in a mathematics lesson. This makes the respondents of this research at-risk and perhaps other uncaptured students in a similar situation.

Figure 2: Students reading mathematics notes at home under parents' supervision

Source: Field data (2022)

In Figure 2, it is very surprising that 60% of the respondents forget almost everything they have been taught in class by their mathematics teachers and cannot remember them at home. Equal percentage of 20 either remember or sometimes remember the content of mathematics they are taught in school. This is a really serious issue of concern that needs to be addressed to facilitate student learning. If forgetfulness of subject matter at this adolescent stage of the students are not remedied, it will negatively affect them in their academics pursuit. Though not specified, it could be attributed to their excessive indulging and spending more time on social media at the expense of their books. Parents are seen not be supervising their children's studies at home (thus, according to Figure 2). In this scenario, the children are left to their fate. This is very serious and as children, they may resort to play with their books and friends around in the house. In Africa, especially in Ghana, children easily make friends to play than to learn something educative.

Figure 3: Students' attention in class during mathematics lessons

Source: Field data (2022)

In Figure 3, students paying attention in class during mathematics lesson is as high as 80% but only 20% sometimes do not pay attention. And this is quite not surprising in education because most education researchers have attributed this type of challenge to poor classroom management (Robinson & Harris, 2014). Again, the figure shows that the students do not dislike the subject mathematics but they do not often ask questions during

the lesson. It is evident that they communicate with their friends during the lesson. It could be that they ask for further explanations from their peers than from the teacher. This peer teaching among students, is possibly making them not to do their mathematics exercises alone in class, thus according Figure 3.

Figure 4: Students' level of preparation before mathematics examinations are written

Source: Field data (2022)

Figure 4 gives more details on the students' preparedness before examination. This figure seems to summarise the challenges that the students are facing that make the at-risk in mathematics. Being it revision, preparation at home, and during mathematics examination. It is quite profound in the instance where the 'at-risk' students say they do not understand their own written mathematics notes some weeks before the examination period begin, making it more difficult for them to work examples on their own. The inability of students to prepare adequately for mathematics examinations can be seen as the grounds for poor students' performance (WAEC-Ghana, 2020). Performance of students in mathematics examination, thus according to the participants of this research clearly reflects Figure 4, which is in line with Armah (2018) and Leung (2002) findings on the attitude and performance of students in mathematics.

5.0 Conclusion

The research paper which sort to enquire the perception and attitude of at-risk students in class supported that students do not understand their mathematics teachers well in class during lessons delivery (Armah, 2018). While the students stay with real parents or relatives, they are not well supervised to read over their maths notes, do assignments, or work more examples in mathematics at home. Again, teachers teaching mathematics have not, or yet to notice that their students do not pay rapt attention in class during lesson delivery. Also, students do not like mathematics examination and for that matter, do not revise adequately for the examinations. To ensure that basic schools in the Wenchi Municipality achieve institutional survival and student performance, teachers and parents need to collaborate and go beyond ordinary teaching and parenting to taking keen interest in total development of the school children, especially the adolescents by addressing most of the educational needs. The following recommendations were made, following the findings: (1) the time spent in school by students should be increased; local dialect should be adopted by maths teachers when teaching; teachers should revise thoroughly with students before, and during examinations; (2) parents should engage their children in learning at home on daily basis; the time spent on television, internet and social media at home should be keenly monitored by parents; if possible, parents could engage the services of home teachers for their children in addressing certain academics challenges. Parents should frequently interact with their children at home to ascertain their difficulties in subject areas; (3) classroom management and control, teaching pedagogy should be revised to arouse the interest of the students in mathematics in order for them to pay attention in class during lesson delivery; (4) teachers should revise thoroughly with students before, and during examinations periods; schools should ensure to take revision periods seriously, since it accounts for the performances students put up during and after examinations.

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